

Effects of Think Pair Share Strategy on Achievement and Retention in Mathematics among Secondary School Students in Osisioma Local Government Area, Abia State

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Abstract

This study investigated effects of think pair share strategy on achievement and retention in mathematics among secondary school students in Osisioma Local Government area, Abia State 1002 (454 male and 548 female) Senior Secondary School two students during 2023/2024 academic session formed the population. The sample comprises of 92 (42 male and 50 female) students drawn from the population using purposive and simple random sampling techniques. Instrument used for data collection was teacher made Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The test items covered 25 objective questions from Word Problems in Linear and Simultaneous Equations. MAT was constructed and validated by experts from mathematics education and measurement and evaluation. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.82 obtained using kuder Richardson (K-R-20). Four research questions were posed and answered using mean and standard deviation while four null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance. The result among others showed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement and retention scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy and those taught using conventional method. It was concluded that the use of Think Pair share strategy is require in teaching of mathematics because students achieved and retained more using it. Based on the result, it was recommended among others that teachers should use Think Pair share strategy to teach mathematics for better achievement and retention.

Keywords: think pair share, achievement, retention, mathematics, strategy.

Introduction

Mathematics in Nigeria education is one of the subjects studied at all levels of education, from primary schools to universities. Mathematics is an indispensable tool in virtually all human endeavors and there is hardly any field where mathematics is not useful (Agwagah, 2013; Uka, 2020). This implies that mathematics is the pillar of all knowledge showing its relevance in all disciplines. That is why Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) has made mathematics a compulsory subject at both primary and secondary school levels in Nigeria. Mathematics is a knowledge that trains the minds into systematic and critical thinking as well as reasoning. It equips learners with the basic knowledge and skills required for further learning in many courses like engineering, medicine, accounting, banking and finance, business administration to mention but a few. In fact mathematics is not only utilized in every field of human endeavor, it plays a fundamental role in educational advancement. In spite of the importance of mathematics in life, some students do not show much seriousness in the subject and still have difficulties in solving mathematic problems (Tanujaya & Mumu, 2019).

The poor performance in mathematics has continue to occur in our external examinations, WAEC (Chief Examiners Reports, 2018-2022). The stake holders in education are so worried because of the position of mathematics in Nigerian Education System. The problem of poor performance has been attributed to many factors; teachers' factors, students' factors and others. Among the teachers' factors is the teaching method applied by the teachers. According to Amadi and Ibekwe (2016), in fostering learning in the classrooms, teachers should bring the learners to close contact with the curriculum contents using appropriate teaching method.

Kurumeh et al (2012) maintained that the inappropriate and inadequate teaching techniques and methods used by mathematics teachers are instrumental to learners' inability to understand and retain basic mathematical principles and computations. Likewise, Digari et al (2016) blamed the poor achievement in mathematics in the use of inappropriate teaching strategy which might lead to lack of retention of mathematics concept.

According to Digari et al (2016), the teaching method implies the use of principles and theories of instructions which can include class participation, demonstrations, recitation. The appropriate teaching methods should be such that can engage students both inside and outside classrooms (Finn & Zimmer in Mundelsi & Jurkowski, 2021). According to them, students with higher levels of engagement inside and outside the classroom not only learn more than students with lower level of engagement, they are also more successful in the long run both academically and professionally. In order words, that method that engages students in the classroom will definitely increase their academic achievements. Such methods include problem solving, guided discovery, ethnomathematics, and Think pair share among others (Garba & Salim 2020; Bitrus et al 2020; Finn & Zimmer in Mundelsi & Jurkowoki, 2021).

In the classrooms today, the traditional strategy of teaching and learning mathematics is still being utilized by teachers (Nwoke, 2015, Garba & Salim, 2020). This traditional strategy of teaching is popularly known as conventional method of teaching which requires the teacher doing most of the talking while the students take note and remain passive. This method of teaching occupies the school system as teachers still use the method in teaching mathematics. It emphasizes teacher centered, teacher- directed instructions and there is a little or no interaction between teachers and students. There is then the need to consider in teaching mathematics the method that engages the students more of which Think Pair Share strategy is among. Think – Pair Share (TPS) is a collaborative learning strategy where students work together to solve a problem. This strategy requires students to: think individually about a topic or answer to a question and share ideas with participation (EL Sevier, 2013). Think pair share, sometimes called “turn and talk”, is one of the best ways for teachers to slow down the conversation and give students time to process their ideas before verbally responding.

According to Echevarria et al (2014), Think Pair Share is a cooperative learning strategy used to easily monitor students understanding of content objectives. It gives all students a chance to think and discuss. It allows them time for individual reflection, thinking and processing new information before they may be influenced by other students’ answer. This process also teaches students how to explain their thoughts first to a peer, and then to a larger audience (the entire class). Think – pair – share was developed by Frank Lyman in 1981. It is the learning tool a teacher can use to help students think independently, pair up and discuss with a classmate or in small groups, and share their knowledge with the class. Think pair share can be used in mathematics as students complete word problems. Students can think about a given word problem and the steps that could be used in order to solve it. Without solving the problem, students can share the problem – solving strategy they thought of with a partner. After discussing, students can solve the problem on their own and compare answer with a partner.

In mathematics, questions that work well with this strategy include word problems, logic problems, estimations and patterns. It has been proven that students may benefit by using peer-mediated interventions which are consistently producing higher academic achievement (Bataineh, 2017).

Academic achievement is an outstanding change in students behavior as a result of their exposure to a specific programme instruction (Orobasa, 2016). Academic achievement has been one of the most important goals of the educational process. It is the overall academic performance of a student in the school. In fact, academic achievement is an index of a child’s future in this competitive world. If this is so, what is learnt needs to be retained.

Retention is defined as the level which an individual is capable to recall an acquired knowledge at any given time. Retention also is the ability to remember experiences and things learnt. This implies that the amount of knowledge learnt and kept, skills maintained or problem-solving behaviours manifested consistently reflects what retention is. Retention in mathematics, therefore is the ability of a learner to keep and remember as well as recall or reproduce the required knowledge or some parts of the knowledge after some period of time must have elapsed. Therefore, to improve students achievement level in mathematics, implies to improve the level at which they retain the concept of mathematics learnt. Hence, the need to investigate if think pair share strategy of learning could improve retention of both male and female students in Mathematics.

Gender is referred to as the social roles that are believed to belong to male and female with a particular social grouping (Amoo & Onasanya, 2017). It is a set of characteristics distinguishing between male and female particularly in the case of man and woman. Gender differences in mathematics achievement and ability has been a serious concern as scientist have observed the under-representation of women in mathematics, physical science and engineering (Asante in Tanujaya & Mumu, 2019). Some researchers found that in using Think Pair share strategy to teach mathematics, that students perform better both in achievement and retention but the male counterpart outshined the female both in achievement and retention (Kaddoura, 2013, Birtus in Bitrus et al 2020, Sanderson et al, 2022).

There are some researchers who found that there is no significant difference in mean achievement and retention scores of students that were taught using Think Pair Share strategy based on gender (Batainah, 2017; Adimora et al 2014). Since there

is a conflicting view of different authors as per students' academic achievement and retention when taught using Think Pair Share strategy and the influence on gender, there.

Despite the importance of mathematics in life, technology and nation development to mention but a few, the poor academic performance of students is on the increase (WAEC Chief Examiners Reports, 2018-2022). Teaching methods have been found as one of the major problems of this poor performance. Many methods of teaching have been introduced by teachers yet the problem persisted. It is observed that the conventional lecture method is still being used in the classroom and it is teacher centered and students are passive. There is need to use a method that will engage students more, make the lesson students – centered to see if students' achievement and retention will improve. Think pair share strategy is a strategy that requires students to think individually about a topic or answer to a question and share with entire class or group.

This study therefore is to investigate the effect of Think-pair-share on students' academic achievement and retention in Mathematics since it has been proven that students may benefit by using peer-mediated interventions like Think-pair-share which are consistently producing higher academic achievement (Bataineh,2017).

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of think pair share strategy on achievement and retention in mathematics among secondary school students. Specifically, the study seeks to find out, the:

1. Mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair share strategy and those taught using conventional method,
2. Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy,
3. Mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy,
4. Mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy.

Research Questions

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy and those taught using conventional method?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy?
3. What are the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy?
4. What are the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-share strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy and those taught using conventional method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share strategy

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share Strategy

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental because of different extraneous variables the researchers may control at the course of this study. Specifically, the pretest-posttest control group design was used. The population of the study was all the senior secondary school students in Osisioma local government area of Abia State which is made up of one thousand and two senior secondary two students.

A sample of Ninety-two (forty two male and fifty female) students were selected using simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used for data collection was researchers' developed achievement test which was validated by three experts from department of science education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for research questions and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

The data were analyzed and the result presented according to research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy and those taught using conventional method?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught mathematics using Think pair share strategy and those taught using conventional method.

Teaching Methods	N	Pretest		Post test		Mean difference
		Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	Mean(\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	
Conventional	44	25.68	3.86	32.77	4.65	7.09
Think Pair Share	48	25.25	4.10	55.13	6.87	29.88

Table 1 showed the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy and those taught using conventional method. Students taught using conventional method had a pretest mean of 25.68 and standard deviation of 3.86 while their posttest means and standard deviation of 32.77 and 4.65 respectively. Students taught using think pair share strategy had pretest mean and standard deviation of 25.25 and 4.10 respectively while their posttest mean and standard deviation are 55.13 and 6.87 respectively. This indicates that students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy achieved better than those taught using conventional method.

Research Question 2

What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share Strategy?

Table 2: Mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share learning strategy.

Gender	N	Pre-Test		Post-Test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	
Male	22	24.73	3.98	56.73	6.06	32.00
Female	26	25.69	4.22	53.77	7.32	28.08

Table 2 showed the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught mathematics using Think-pair-Share learning strategy. From table 2, the pretest mean scores for male and female were 24.73 and 25.69 respectively while their standard deviation are 3.98 and 4.22 respectively. The posttest means scores for male and female were 56.73 and 53.77 respectively while their standard deviation scores are 6.06 and 7.32 respectively. This indicates that the male students had a higher mean gain than their female counterparts. This implies the male students performed better than the female students when taught mathematics using Think Pair Share learning strategy.

Research Question 3

What are the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair-Share learning strategy?

Table 3: Mean retention scores and standard deviation of students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share learning strategy.

Teaching Method	N	Post test		Retention		Mean difference
		Mean(\bar{x})	Std. Dev	Mean(\bar{x})	Std. Dev	

Think pair share	48	55.13	6.87	59.38	6.07	4.25
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Table 3 showed the mean retention scores and standard deviations of the students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy. The posttest had mean of 55.13 with standard deviation of 6.87 and retention mean of 59.38 with standard deviation of 6.07. The mean difference is 4.25. This indicates that the means were not far from each other which indicates that the students retained what they were taught.

Research Question 4

What are the mean retention scores of male and female students taught using Think-Pair-Share strategy?

Table 4: Mean retention scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught using Think-Pair-Share strategy?

Gender	N	Post-Test		Retention		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	
Male	22	55.13	6.87	58.64	6.37	3.51
Female	26	53.77	7.32	60.15	5.80	6.38

Table 4 revealed that the mean post test score and standard deviation of male students are 55.13 and 6.87 respectively while that of female are 53.77 and 7.32 respectively. The table further shows that the mean retention score and standard deviation of the male students are 58.64 and 6.37 respectively while that of female students are 60.15 and 5.80 respectively. The table also revealed that the female students had a higher mean gain of 6.38 than the male students with mean gain of 3.51. This implies that female students developed retention higher than their male counterparts when taught with Think Pair Share strategy in mathematics.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share and those taught using conventional method.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the mean Achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy and those taught using conventional method.

Source	Type Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	11493.156 ^a	2	5746.578	163.849	.000
Intercept	3560.103	1	3560.103	101.507	.000
Pretest	23.524	1	23.524	.673	.415
Teaching methods	11492.134	1	11492.134	327.668	.000
Error	3121.453	89	35.073		
Total	196264.00	92			
Corrected Total	14614.609	91			

a. R Squared = .786(Adjusted R Squared = .782)

Table 5 showed the F – ratio of 327.668 for groups with P-value of .000 which is less than the significant value of 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is therefore rejected which indicates that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share and those taught using conventional method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy.

Table 6: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of males and females mean scores when taught using Think Pair Share learning strategy

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	101.861 ^a	2	50.931	1.408	.255
Intercept	3345.471	1	3345.411	92.506	.000
Post think pair	79.702	1	79.702	2.204	.145
Gender	7.067	1	7.067	.195	.661
Error	1627.389	45	36.164		
Total	170948.000	48			
Corrected Total	1729.250	47			

a. R Square = .059 (Adjusted R Squared = .017)

The result in Table 6 showed F-ratio of .195 with P-value of .661 which is greater than the significant value of 0.05. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share strategy

Table 7: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the mean Retention scores of students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share learning strategy.

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	94.794 ^a	1	94.794	2.668	.109
Intercept	3597.318	1	3597.318	101.243	.000
Post think pair	94.794	1	94.794	2.668	
Error	1634.456	46	35.532		
Total	170948.000	48			
Corrected Total	1729.250	47			

a. R Squared = .055 (Adjusted R Squared = .034)

The result in Table 7 shows F-ratio of 2.668 with P-value of .109 which is greater than the significant value of 0.05. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the retention score of students taught mathematics using think pair share is accepted. This implies there is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy.

Table 8: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of male and female students mean retention scores when taught using think pair share strategy.

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	71.583 ^a	2	35.792	.978	.384
Intercept	3095.340	1	3095.340	84.606	.000
Think post	44.142	1	44.142	1.207	.278
Gender	13.485	1	13.485	.369	.547
Error	1646.333	45	36.585		
Total	171412.000	48			

a. R Squared=.042 (Adjusted R Squared= .001)

The result in Table 8 showed F-ratio of .369 with P-value of .547 which is greater than the significant value of 0.05. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that students who were taught using think pair share learning strategy performed better than students who were taught through conventional method. The male students performed better than their female counterpart. The students also retained what they learnt through think pair share learning strategy. The female students developed retention higher than the male students. The study showed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy and those taught using conventional method. This is in agreement with the findings of Kaddoara (2013), Birtus et al (2020) and Sanderson et al (2022) whose research works indicated that students who learnt through think-pair-share strategy performed better than their counterparts both in achievement and retention in mathematics.

This study also showed that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement and retention scores male and female students taught mathematics using think-pair-share strategy though the males achieved higher but the females retained more. This is in line with the findings of Batainah, 2017; Adimora, et al, 2014 whose studies found out that there is no significant difference in achievement and retention based on gender for students taught using think pair share strategy .But this finding contradicts the findings of Kaddoara (2013), Birtus et al (2020) and Sanderson et al (2022) whose work found that male counterparts achieved and retained more while the present work found that the males achieved more but the females retained more.

Conclusions

From the results obtained in the study, it was found that students taught mathematics using think pair share performed better than their counterparts taught using conventional method. The students taught mathematics using think pair share retained what they were taught. Male students performed better than female students though not significant. Female students developed retention higher than their male counterparts when taught with think pair share strategy though not significant.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proffered

1. Teachers should adopt think pair share learning strategy in teaching since it has been found to enhance retention and achievement in mathematics.
2. Teachers should teach male and female students equally using think pair share learning strategy both need for better achievement and retention.
3. Workshops should be organized for teachers by state and federal government, Associations like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN). This is because some teachers may not be aware of how best to employ think pair share learning strategy.

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